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ANNOTATION

Candidiasis or oral candidosis is one of the most common human opportunistic fungal infections of the oral cavity. This pathology has a wide variety of treatment which has been studied until these days. The present study offers a literature review on the treatment of oral candidiasis, with the purpose of establish which treatment is the most suitable in each case. Searching the 24 latest articles about treatment of candidiasis it concluded that the incidence depends on the type of the candidiasis and the virulence of the infection.

Keywords: orthopedic cases, diagnosis, dental treatment, oral candidiasis.

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OG'IZ KANDIDOZINI TASHXISLASH VA DAVOLASHNING ZAMONAVIY MUAMMOLARI

ANNOTATSIYA

Kandidoz yoki og'iz kandidozi og'iz bo'shlig'ining eng keng tarqalgan inson organizmidagi qo'ziqorin infeksiyalaridan biridir. Ushbu patologiya shu kungacha o'rganilgan turli xil davolash usullariga ega. Ko'plab tadqiqotlar og'iz kandidozini davolash bo'yicha adabiyotlarni ko'rib chiqishni taklif qiladi, har bir holatda qaysi davolash eng mos ekanligini aniqlangan.

Kalit so'zlar: ortopedik holatlar, diagnostika, terapevtik davolash, og'iz kandidozi.

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СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ ПРОБЛЕМЫ ДИАГНОСТИКИ И ЛЕЧЕНИЯ КАНДИДОЗА ПОЛОСТИ РТА

АННОТАЦИЯ

Кандидоз полости рта является одной из наиболее распространенных оппортунистических грибковых инфекций полости рта у человека. Эта патология имеет широкий спектр методов лечения, которые были изучены до настоящего времени. В настоящем исследовании представлен обзор литературы по лечению кандидоза полости рта с целью определения того, какое лечение является наиболее подходящим в каждом конкретном случае.

Ключевые слова: ортопедические случаи, диагностика, стоматологическое лечение, кандидоз полости рта.

Relevance.

Oral candidiasis (sometimes called "candidiasis stomatitis" or "oropharyngeal candidiasis") is a lesion of the oral cavity by a fungal infection of the genus *Candida*. Inflammation can cover the entire oral cavity or its individual parts — tongue, lips, gums, palate — and also spread to the tonsils and throat (including larynx). Oral candidiasis occurs with a decrease in immunity and most often worries children, the elderly and pregnant women.

As a rule, oropharyngeal candidiasis occurs in the form of thrush — inflammation with the formation of a characteristic curd or film-like plaque of white, grayish or yellowish color.

Causes of the disease

Oral candidiasis develops due to the fact that *Candida* fungi, which are normally found on the skin and mucous membranes of healthy people, begin to actively grow. This happens if the immune system is reduced: normal microflora cannot effectively restrain the growth of fungi and they begin to actively multiply, provoking an inflammatory process in the affected area.

A decrease in immunity can be caused by age-related or hormonal causes, pathological disorders, deficiency of vitamins and minerals, taking certain medications and other factors.

Factors that contribute to the development of oral candidiasis:

inflammatory processes in the mouth — stomatitis of a non-fungal nature, untreated carious cavities, gum disease;

chronic diseases of the genitourinary system (including syphilis, trichomoniasis);

endocrine diseases (thyroid pathology, diabetes mellitus);

diseases of the gastrointestinal tract;

immunodeficiency conditions (defects of immune cells, HIV);

autoimmune diseases;

long-term treatment with antibacterial and/or corticosteroid drugs;

the use of hormonal contraceptives for a long time;

pregnancy (especially the third trimester);

childhood;

prematurity;

chronic diseases in infants (including rickets);

chronic deficiency of vitamins and minerals;

old age.

Against the background of reduced immunity, injuries and microtrauma of the oral mucosa can lead to the development of candidiasis.

Diagnosis and treatment of oral candidiasis is an urgent problem of dentistry, which is determined by the significant prevalence of fungal infection. Thus, according to WHO, up to 20% of the world's population has suffered various forms of candida infection at least once during their lifetime [2].

Recently, the incidence of oral candidiasis has been steadily increasing. This is due to a number of predisposing factors, such as the uncontrolled use of broad-spectrum antibacterial drugs, prolonged use of corticosteroids, as well as an increase in the number of patients with endocrine pathology, hypovitaminosis, and immunodeficiency conditions [4]. Despite significant advances in scientific research in the field of fungal disease therapy, the diagnosis and treatment of oral

candidiasis is a difficult clinical task for a doctor. Dentists often make mistakes in the examination and treatment of patients with oral candidiasis, which negatively affects the outcome of the disease.

The purpose of the study.

The purpose of this study was to identify and analyze medical errors made in the diagnosis and treatment of oral candidiasis.

Research material and methods.

On the basis of the Department of Orthopedic Dentistry of the Samarkand State Medical University, 60 patients (42 women and 18 men) aged 31 to 55 years were examined and treated, who were referred for consultation from dental clinics in Volgograd and the region with a diagnosis of oral candidiasis.

Clinical and laboratory methods were used in the examination of patients. Clinical research methods included the collection of patient complaints and anamnesis, taking into account data from medical history statements submitted by the medical institution for consultation, assessment of the clinical course of the disease, identification of medical errors in the diagnosis and treatment of oral candidiasis. Dental examination of patients was carried out according to a generally accepted scheme, including an examination of the oral mucosa (color, humidity, presence and localization of lesion elements) and an assessment of the condition of the teeth (lack of oral sanitation, the presence of dental deposits, the presence and quality of orthopedic structures). The hygienic condition was determined using the Green—Vermillion index.

Laboratory methods included clinical and biochemical blood analysis, as well as microbiological tests to detect changes in the composition of the microbiocenosis of the oral cavity and intestines. To identify concomitant pathology, patients were recommended to consult an endocrinologist, gastroenterologist, immunologist, and therapist.

After the examination, patients were prescribed treatment aimed at eliminating the causative agent of the disease and normalizing the immune system, as well as desensitizing therapy. The course of treatment for candidiasis was 21 days.

Research results and discussion.

The data of the consultation made it possible to identify a number of medical errors made by dentists in the diagnosis and treatment of oral candidiasis. In 5 patients, the diagnosis of oral candidiasis was made incorrectly, while three of them had lichen planus exudatively hyperemic, and 2 patients had flat leukoplakia.

During the dental examination of patients, dentists did not pay due attention to the state of oral hygiene and the availability of sanitation.

Although chronic injury to the oral mucosa by sharp edges of teeth, poor-quality dentures, destroyed crowns refers to factors that provoke the development of oral candidiasis, and should be eliminated first. However, 98% of patients referred for consultation had an unsatisfactory hygienic condition of the oral cavity ($IGR-Y = 2.8 \pm 0.2$), an abundance of dental deposits, and lack of oral sanitation. Doctors did not take into account that it is the level of the functional system of the oral cavity of each individual, taking into account hygienic skills, traumatic factors, that characterizes the ecosystem as a whole.

Only 7 patients were referred for consultations by an endocrinologist, gastroenterologist, of whom 4 patients ignored an appeal to an endocrinologist.

Dentists should remember that oral candidiasis is often the first and only clinical sign of asymptomatic diabetes mellitus.

Therefore, consultation with an endocrinologist is an obligatory step in the examination of patients with candidiasis. The majority of patients (86%) were not examined at all to identify concomitant pathology. Concomitant diseases were detected in all the consulted patients. Diseases of the gastrointestinal tract were diagnosed in 72% of patients, endocrinopathy (diabetes mellitus, hypothyroidism) - in 28% of the subjects.

An analysis of 94% of extracts from medical records submitted for consultation revealed the absence of laboratory methods: clinical and biochemical blood tests, as well as microbiological tests to detect changes in the composition of the microbiocenosis of the oral cavity and intestines.

However, the diagnosis of oral candidiasis should be comprehensive and include not only clinical, but also laboratory methods, the leading of which is microbiological.

When choosing a drug for systemic therapy, its effect on the pathogen (fungistatic or fungicidal), as well as on the macroorganism, was not evaluated (both the state of the immune system and individual sensitivity to this substance were not taken into account). In 2/3 of the patients, treatment was prescribed without taking into account these results of bacteriological inoculation for sensitivity to drugs. Taking into account the growing resistance of *Candida* to antimycotic drugs, currently systemic therapy should be prescribed only taking into account the sensitivity of the pathogen. According to the results of bacteriological culture, 83% of the consulted patients showed high sensitivity to fluconazole, 17% to itraconazole.

Indications for the use of systemic antimycotic therapy were ignored, primarily a certain clinical form of the lesion (acute pseudomembranous candidiasis, clinical signs of dissemination, chronic forms of the disease resistant to previously administered local therapy). In a number of patients, only local antimycotic therapy was used, however, local drugs act only on the surface of the oral mucosa, reducing the manifestations of candidiasis, while the elimination of the pathogen is often not achieved.

The treatment regimen for all patients with oral candidiasis did not include therapy aimed at increasing the immunological resistance of the body. It is known that with candidiasis, the digestibility of vitamins and minerals, especially iron, decreases sharply. Therefore, the optimal drug in this case is Ferroglobin B12, a complex containing iron, vitamins B and C, folic and panthenonic acids, as well as licorice root extract, which has a stimulating effect on nonspecific resistance of the body.

None of the patients were prescribed probiotics. It has been proven that prolonged use of antibiotics not only violates the composition of the resident microflora of the oral cavity, but can also cause intestinal dysbiosis, resulting in hypovitaminosis of groups B, C, PP, which, in turn, negatively affects the functional state of the oral mucosa (it becomes susceptible to candida infection). Competitive probiotics are highly effective in the fight against candida infection.

Competitive probiotics are highly effective in the fight against candida infection.

Their use is due to antagonistic properties relative to fungi of the genus *Candida*, which are realized through competition for nutrient substrates and the synthesis of anti-candida metabolites. Our clinical experience confirms the high effectiveness of the self-eliminating probiotic Bactistatin [1]. Thus, in addition to antimycotic therapy, all patients did not receive additional treatment aimed at correcting the immune mechanisms of the body.

Conclusion.

The analysis of errors made by dentists in the diagnosis and treatment of oral candidiasis indicates an underestimation of the risk factors for candidiasis, a misunderstanding of the pathogenesis of the disease, and a one-sided presentation of candidiasis as a local pathological process.

Currently, candidiasis should be considered as an immune deficiency condition resulting from a deep imbalance of the ecosystem as a whole. Such an idea of the disease determines the fundamental need for an integrated approach to the diagnosis and treatment of candidiasis. Therapy aimed at all links of the pathological process makes it possible to increase the effectiveness of treatment and, in addition, contributes to achieving a long period of remission of the disease [3].

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